

DIFFICULTIES IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL LEVEL

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1.1 Abstract:

Research is simply the process of arriving dependable solution to problem through the planned and systematic collection, analysis and interpretation of the data. Truly research is an important tool for the advancement of knowledge as well promotion of the progress. Teacher is important factor in teaching process. Some teachers have the inborn qualities of teaching and have a good command on the subject, but all are not blessed they face various difficulties while teaching so the teaching can be made effective by understanding it or by the study of the difficulties arising while teaching. Research is oriented towards the discovery of the relationship that exist among the phenomena of the world and the term Educational Research is restricted to the systemic study designed to provide the educators with the more effective means of attaining the worthwhile educational goals .Research has no doubt proved to be an essential as well as the powerful tool in leading man toward progress.

1.2Introduction:

Mathematics is an immortal and hard subject. Concept new laws, rules properties and method are given importance in teaching of Mathematics. Teacher must try to teach this subject effectively, interestingly should check achievements of his objectives in teaching these things are expected for the achievement of these objectives. Various type of content are included in the syllabus. Students also vary in their mental capacity and interest in Mathematics. So the teacher must plan to try their level best to make children understand the lesson properly and should feel

newness in teaching. Learning of the students is mostly depended upon teacher. Inventive attitude and way of the representing content that is going to be taught.

1.3 Meaning Of The Research

A research is a process involves a number of inter related activities or operations that overlap continuously rather than follow a prescribed sequence. The operations involved in the research process are so interdependent that the earlier steps. It is obvious that each one of the various operations will have an effect on the quality of research. A small omission anywhere will affect the quality of study just a small lapse will affect the satisfaction of the people from a recipe.

1.4 Conceptual Terms

1. Mathematics: It is one of the compulsory subject from the secondary level syllabus.
2. Name of City: Miraj city of Miraj Taluka.

1.5 Objective Of The Research

1. To find the difficulties in teaching Mathematics teachers of the secondary school level.
2. To compare the difficulties of teaching Mathematics teacher for the secondary school level.

1.6 Scope And Limitations

1. This Research is limited only for the Mathematics teachers.
2. This Research is limited only for the secondary level of the schools.
3. This Research is useful for the educational institute and the teachers of Mathematics that teach to the secondary classes.
- 4 This Research is limited only for the secondary level of the schools in Miraj city.

1.7 Research Method

Survey method is used for the present Research.

1.8 Research Tool:

In this present research Self prepared questionnaires was used.

1.7 Sample For Research :

In this Research the teachers of Miraj city who teach Mathematics subject at secondary level are selected. The total number of secondary school teachers is 21. The sample of mathematics teachers is 21.

1.10 Analysis and Interpretation

Table no 1

Percentage of Duration for solving examples in Class Room

Sr.No.	Duration for Solving examples in Class Room.	Able to give	Unable to give	Partly	Total
1.	Number of teachers	18	0	3	21
2.	Percentage	96%	0%	4%	100%

Observation:

In the above table no.1 it is observed that the number of the teachers who are able to give time duration for solving examples in class room is 18 and their percent is 96 %. And those who are unable to give is 0 and their percentage is 0% and partly is 3 and their percentage is 4%.

Interpretation:

The number of teachers who are able to give time duration for solving examples in class room is maximum.

Table no 2

Percentage of Response of Students in teaching

Sr.No.	Response of Students in teaching	Able to get response	Unable to get response	Partly	Total
1.	Number of teachers	14	0	7	21
2.	Percentage	67%	0%	33%	100%

Observation:

In the above table no.2 it is observed that the number of the teachers who are able to get proper response in teaching is 14 and their percent is 67%. And those are unable to get is 0 and their percentage is 0% and partly is 7 and their percent is 33%.

Interpretation:

The number of teachers who are able to get proper response in teaching is maximum.

TableNo.3

Percentage of Re-teaching for the Absent students

Sr.No.	Re-teaching for the Absent students	Able to re-teach	Unable to re-teach	Partly	Total
1.	Number of teachers	6	3	12	21
2.	Percentage	28.53%	14.23%	57.24%	100%

Observation:

In the above table no.3 it is observed that the number of the teachers who are able to re-teach for the absent students is 6 and their percent is 28.53%. And those are unable to re-teach is 3 and their percentage is 14.23% and partly is 12 and their percent is 57.24%.

Interpretation:

The number of teachers who are able to re-teach for the absent students is maximum.

TableNo.4

Percentage of teachers giving Various Projects on Mathematics subject

Sr.No.	Various Projects on Mathematics subject	Able to give	Unable to give	Partly	Total
1.	Number of teachers	11	0	10	21
2.	Percentage	53%	0%	47%	100%

Observation:

In the above table no.4 it is observed that the number of the teachers that who are able to give various projects on Mathematics subject is 11 and their percent is 53%. And those are unable to give is 0 and their percentage is 0% and partly is 57.62 and their percent is 47%.

Interpretation:

The number of teachers who are able to give various projects on Mathematics subject is maximum.

TableNo.5

Percentage of Remedial Teaching for Intellectually Backward students

Sr.No.	Remedial Teaching for Intellectually Backward students	Able to teach	Unable to teach	Partly	Total
1.	Number of teachers	15	0	6	21
2.	Percentage	71.42%	0%	28.57%	100%

Observation:

In the above table no.5 it is observed that the number of the teachers that are able to take remedial teaching for intellectually backward students is 15 and their percent is 71.42%. And those are unable to take is 0 and their percentage is 0% and partly is 6 and their percentage is 28.57%.

Interpretation:

The number of teachers who are able to take the remedial teaching for intellectually backward students is maximum.

TableNo.6

Percentage of teachers who make use of New Techniques for Solving Theorems from Geometry

Sr.No.	New Techniques for Solving Theorems	Able to use	Unable to use	Partly	Total
1.	Number of teachers	16	0	5	21
2.	Percentage	76.19%	0%	23.81%	100%

Observation:

In the above table no.6 it is observed that the number of the teacher that able to make use of new techniques for solving theorems from Geometry is 16 and their percent is 76.19%. And those are unable to make use is 0 and their percentage is 0% and partly is 5 and their percentage 23.81%.

Interpretation:

The number of teachers who are able to make use of the new techniques for solving theorems from Geometry is maximum.

TableNo.7

Percentage of teachers who Lose Control over Class while teaching Geometry

Sr.No.	lose control over class while teaching Geometry	Able to control	Unable to control	Partly	Total
1.	Number of teachers	18	0	3	21
2.	Percentage	85.72%	0%	14.28%	100%

Observation:

In the above table no.7 it is observed that the number of the teachers that are able to control over class while teaching Geometry is 18 and their percent is 85.72%. And those are unable to control is 0 and their percentage is 0% and partly is 3 and their percentage 14.28%

Interpretation:

The number of teachers who are able to control over class while teaching Geometry is maximum.

TableNo.8

Percentage of Students- Teachers Interaction

Sr.No.	Students Teachers Interaction	Able to interact	Unable to interact	Partly	Total
1.	Number of teachers	15	0	6	21
2.	Percentage	71.43%	0%	28.57%	100%

Observation:

In the above table no.8 it is observed the number of the teachers that are able to interact with the students easily is 15 and their percent is 71.43%. And those are unable to interact is 0 and their percentage is 0% and partly is 6 & their percentage 28.57%

Interpretation:

The number of teachers who are able to interact with the students easily is maximum.

TableNo9

Percentage of teachers who follow Continuous Comprehensive

Evaluation Method for students

Sr.No.	Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation Method	Able to follow	Unable to follow	Partly	Total
1.	Number of teachers	16	0	5	21
2.	Percentage	76.20%	0%	23.80%	100%

Observation:

In the above table no.9 it is observed that the number of the teachers that are able to follow continuous comprehensive evaluation method for students is 16 and their percent is 76.20%. And those are unable to follow is 0 and their percentage is 0% and partly is 5 and their percentage 23.80%

Interpretation:

The number of teachers who are able to follow continuous comprehensive evaluation method for students is maximum.

TableNo.10

Percentage of teachers who give Assignment Related to Creative and Interesting Content

Sr.No.	Assignment Related to Creative and Interesting Content	Able to give	Unable to give	Partly	Total
1.	Number of teachers	15	0	6	21
2.	Percentage	71.43%	0%	28.57%	100%

Observation:

In the above table no. 10 it is observed that the number of the teachers that are able to give assignment related to creative and interesting content is 15 and their percent is 71.43%. And those are unable to give is 0 and their percentage is 0% and partly is 6 and their percentage 28.57%

Interpretation:

The number of teachers who are able to give the assignment related to creative and interesting content is maximum.

TableNo.11

**Percentage of Fulfillment of Objective According to Unit
after Completion of Lesson**

Sr.No.	Fulfillment of Objective According to Unit after Completion of Lesson	Able to fulfill	Unable to fulfill	Partly	Total
1.	Number of teachers	12	0	9	21
2.	Percentage	57.15%	0%	42.85%	100%

Observation:

In the above table no.11 it is observed that the number of the teachers that are able to fulfill the objective according to unit after completion of lesson 12 and their percent is 57.15%. And those are unable to fulfill is 0 and their percentage is 0 and partly is 9 and their percentage 42.85%

Interpretation:

The number of teachers who are able to fulfill the objective according to unit after completion of lesson is maximum.

**Table No. 12
Percentage of Teacher Who Clear Doubts**

Sr.No.	Teacher Who Clear Doubts	Able to clear	Unable to clear	Partly	Total
1.	Number of teachers	21	0	0	21
2.	Percentage	100%	0%	0%	100%

Observation:

In the above table no.12 it is observed that the number of the teachers that are able to clear doubts asked by the students 21 and their percent is 100%. And those are unable to clear is 0 and their percentage is 0% and partly is 0 and their percentage 0%

Interpretation:

The number of teachers who are able to clear doubts asked by the students is maximum.

**Table No. 13
Percentage of Teacher who Increase Interest in Learning**

Sr.No.	Increase Interest in Learning	Able to increase	Unable to increase	Partly	Total
1.	Number of teachers	21	0	0	21
2.	Percentage	100%	0%	0%	100%

Observation:

In the above table no.13 it is observed that the number of the teachers that are able to increase interest in learning due to interesting method of teaching is 21 and their percent is

100%. And those unable to increase is 0 and their percentage is 0% and partly is 0 and their percentage 0%

Interpretation:

The number of teacher who are able to increase interest in learning due to interesting method of teaching is maximum.

1.11 Conclusion And Findings :

- The number of teachers who are able to give time duration for solving examples in class room is maximum.
- The number of teachers who are able to get proper response in teaching is maximum.
- The number of teachers who are able to re-teach for the absent students is maximum.
- The number of teachers who are able to give various projects on Math's subject is maximum.
- The number of teachers who are able to take the remedial teaching for intellectually backward students is maximum.
- The number of teachers who are able to make use of new techniques for solving theorems from Geometry is maximum.
- The number of teachers who are able to control over class while teaching Geometry is maximum.
- The number of teachers who are able to interact with the students easily is maximum.
- The number of teachers who are able to follow continuous comprehensive evaluation method for students is maximum.

- The number of teachers who are able to give the assignment related to creative and interesting content is maximum.
- The number of teachers who are able to fulfill the objective according to unit after completion of lesson is maximum.
- The number of teachers who are able to clear doubts asked by the students is maximum.
- The number of teachers who are able to increase interest in learning due to interesting method of teaching is maximum.

1.13 Recommendations

1. This research is helpful in solving the difficulties faced by the teacher of secondary school level in teaching Mathematics.
2. In secondary school level use of advance technological apparatus and computer will be effective to the students.
3. This research is useful for the educational institutions, teachers and schools of secondary level.

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